

INFLUENCE OF EVOLVING TECHNOLOGY ON ADMINISTRATIVE SERVICE DELIVERY IN TERTIARY INSTITUTIONS: EVIDENCE FROM OGUN STATE, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the influence of Evolving Technology on Administrative Service Delivery in selected Tertiary Institutions in Ogun State, Nigeria. The study employed the survey approach with the use of questionnaires as instrument for data collection. The population comprised of all Registry Staff in the two polytechnics covered (The Federal Polytechnic Ilaro and Moshood Abiola Polytechnic, Abeokuta, Ogun State) from which a sample of Two hundred and sixty-five (265) administrative staff were selected using systematic sampling technique. Data collected were analyzed using descriptive and inferential analysis involving linear regression at 0.05 level of significance. Findings revealed that the selected polytechnics have adopted evolving technologies for administrative activities and services and that such technological use has contributed to quality service delivery. It was concluded that the selected polytechnics and other tertiary Institutions should leverage on evolving technologies to streamline their administrative processes to meet the expectations of stakeholders (students, ex-students, other institutions, organizations, management staff, faculty members, vendors, suppliers, etc.) in administrative services delivered. It was recommended that stakeholders, most especially students, ex-students and staff, should be open for training so as to improve on how to use the evolving technologies in order to have quick access to the services being offered by the institution

Keywords: Evolving Technology, Service Delivery, Administrative Staff, Tertiary Institutions.
JEL Codes: I23, M15, O33

1. INTRODUCTION

Both private and public organisations are adopting technology for effective practices and focusing on strategic management that employs digital technology to carry out different activities to steer better performance. The evolution of Technology in the 21st century has affected the administrative services been rendered by Tertiary institutions. The adoption and application of evolving technologies (Anyagou & Okundalaiye, 2025) such as computers, internet, teleconferencing apps, social media, email, phones in all areas of administration are important in tertiary institutions in order to improve service delivery (Ademola & Omobolanle, 2025). These technologies address the problems associated with the old traditional method of carrying out administrative and ancillary functions of day-to-day activities and help to improve service delivery. These Technological Tools are changing the ways service delivery has been rendered (Okereke et al., 2025; Yoon et al., 2026). Routine administrative tasks being carried

out manually are now being handled with evolving technology (Joshua, Joshua & Ikiroma, 2014; Ohakwe, 2001; Abdulkadir, 2017; Ugbo & Chukwuemeka, 2020)

Service delivery is a crucial activity for continuous organizational vision and mission attainment which sustains mission accomplishment, employees' performance, improvement on group abilities and individual competencies ((Adisa & Bamidele, 2024; Kabiru et al., 2023); Jolaade & Kehinde, 2023). The business landscape is dynamic, and trends evolve rapidly, employees in tertiary institution need to foster an agile mindset within the organization to adapt quickly to changes and continuously refine approach to trend integration as tertiary institutions plays a significant roles steering transition and bringing about necessary adjustments (Jimoh et al., 2025). Service delivery, a fundamental aspect of any business or organization, is the process of providing services that meet or exceed customer expectations. It encompasses delivering the right service at the right time, in the right way, and at the right place to ensure customer satisfaction and organizational success. Understanding customer needs and expectations is the cornerstone of effective service delivery. Market research, feedback collection, and customer behavior analysis are essential in comprehending and tailoring services to meet customer requirements (Zeithaml, Bitner, & Gremler, 2016).

The degree to which a person, department, or unit of an organisation fulfils their mandated or assigned duties is known as service delivery. Additionally, it is a way for an organisation to assess the input and output level of a single worker or unit, particularly with regard to achieving predetermined objectives or assigned tasks (Kingsley et al., 2022). It is the degree to which an employee accomplishes the tasks that made his or her job. Service delivery is the degree of an organization and/or employee performance, output and productivity in the discharge of their responsibilities within the available time, money and other resources, towards the achievement of overall goals of the organization (Antony et al 2007).

In this evolving technological era, data is not merely a by-product; it's a strategic asset. Technological advancements equip employees with powerful data analytics tools that unveil patterns, trends, risks and insights (Zhou et al., 2026). This analytical enlightenment transforms administrative decision-making processes, enabling administrators to forecast future needs, optimize resource allocation, and navigate the complexities of a rapidly evolving business landscape with informed precision and this has helped in the quality of administrative services been delivered in tertiary Institutions.

The way and manner in which administrative service is rendered in tertiary institutions have undergone changes over time. Previously, administrative service delivery was carried out in the traditional way which is characterized highly by bureaucratic method with much paperwork and long procedures. The result shows a poor unkempt office where a lot of resources like human, time, paper, were wasted; also, there was delay in services rendered, poor quality services and this give rise to laziness, lack of transparency and corruption (Amukugo & Peters, 2016, Arkes, 2015). There were a lot of complaints from students, staff and other stakeholders who needed one piece of information or another but could not have access to it due to poor delivery of administrative services. With the influx of Technologies in the business world, traditional methods of service delivery have been replaced, and a lot of administrative services are rendered using the evolving technologies (Jimoh & Kehinde, 2025).

Some of the administrative services rendered by Tertiary Institutions using evolving Technology include, admission process, online registration, school fee payment, result management, routine administration such as records keeping, and information dissemination. Others include Computer based Test and examination. Using Technology in work-related

activities reduces waste of time, and mistakes on the part of workers in the discharge of their duties which are more beneficial to tertiary institutions (Jimoh & Kehinde, 2025; Chukwuemeka, Ubochi & Okechukwu, 2017). Effective service delivery prompts public comprehension of the exact services organizations rendered to equal their expectations (Jolaade & Kehinde, 2023, Jimoh & Banjo, 2018)

Evolving Technology is about tools, apps, devices which are used in the varying administrative culture which necessitates the engagement of employees that stimulates the commitment and transparency where the organisation is profitable and in which service delivery plays a vital role (Carter 2018). Haigh, T. (2006) elucidates that every employee that offers administrative service needs to embrace a growth mind-set that emphasises flexible thinking needed to thrive in a constantly changing environment. Technologies used for service delivery improve efficiency, reduce process costs and provide better service for citizens (Jimoh & Kehinde, 2025; Akpomi & Ordu, 2019). It supports more efficient execution of administrative processes by automatically stating the next task in a process or forwarding tasks to the organisational unit which is supposed to further work on a case to minimize waiting times.

Administrative service can now be carried out anywhere and time with the aid of evolving technological devices and internet facilities (Madu et al., 2024). Evolving Technology empowers real-time task management, instant communication, and access to critical information, ensuring that administrators remain agile and responsive even while on the move. This mobile mastery aligns with the modern workforce's demand for flexibility, on-the-go productivity and efficient service delivery. Technology improves the process of service delivery consistently maintains its strong reputation of quality service to regularly meet customer service expectations and also keeps a good administrative environment that has a compatible automation system that will assist in enhancing employee work satisfaction (Jimoh & Kehinde, 2025; Henry, 2014). It provides opportunities for the employees and ensure efficient service delivery and enhanced quality of life (Danda, 2004).

Tertiary institutions have introduced in different areas the use of electronic medium in the administration of their institutions. The use of Technology as enhance information dissemination, teaching, learning, research and public service delivery. Digital administrative service delivery will ensure that staff are no longer passive in the discharge of their duties, instead would decide on the kind of services they want and structure which could best provide the same (Sharma, 2010). Evolving Technology has brought educational revolution that has changed the process and quality of services being rendered. This study therefore examines the influence of Evolving Technology on Administrative Service Delivery in Tertiary Institutions in Ogun State.

In recent years, there has been an increase interest on how the evolving Technology is affecting administration in tertiary institution and which in turn as an effect on the service delivery of employees at all levels. Processes such as payment of fees, Admission Registration of students, planning events and meetings, records keeping, minutes writing, passing of information has still been carried out manually in some tertiary institutions. Technological tools and devices (computers, internet facilities android phones) and teleconferencing devices/app (Zoom, google meet, social media platforms) are available but some of these employees are not willing to adopt to the use of these tools and this as affected the quality of service been delivered. This study therefore aims to examine the effects of evolving technology on administrative service delivery in selected Tertiary Institution in Ogun State

2. METHODOLOGY

This study adopts quantitative approach to survey two selected tertiary institutions in Ogun State with the population focusing on registry staff in The Federal Polytechnic, Ilaro and Moshood Abiola Polytechnic, Abeokuta. At the time of this study, there were 804 registry Staff in these selected Tertiary institutions, 432 (54%) in The Federal Polytechnic, Ilaro and 372 (46%) in Moshood Abiola Polytechnic, Abeokuta. However, a sample size of 265 were selected using Krejcie and Morgan method of sample determination at 0.05 margin error. Multistage approach was adopted for sample selection, and the sample size was allocated proportionately to each of the two schools, making 142 and 123 from The Federal Polytechnic, Ilaro and Moshood Abiola Polytechnic, Abeokuta respectively. Systematic sampling technique was then used to select the staff from each school. A structured questionnaire consisting of Thirty-Eight (38) items with 4-point likert options was used as the instrument of data collection. Data collected were analyzed using descriptive and inferential methods with linear regression at 0.05 level of significance in the Institution. The study took into cognizance gender in the selection of the respondents. Two hundred and sixty-five (265) questionnaires were produced and administered on the respondents but only two hundred and thirty-three (233) copies were duly filled, retrieved and used for data analysis, data collected was then subjected to descriptive and inferential analysis with linear regression at 0.05 level of significance.

3. RESULTS

Table : Evolving Technology Tools/App/Device used for Administrative Service delivery

Descriptive Statistics

	N	Range	Minimum	Maximum	Mean		Std. Deviation	Variance
	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Std. Error	Statistic	Statistic
Zoom	233	3	1	4	3.03	.043	.649	.421
Google Meet	233	3	1	4	2.84	.049	.746	.557
WhatsApp	233	3	1	4	2.77	.042	.646	.418
Telegram	233	3	1	4	1.81	.056	.862	.744
Meetio	233	3	1	4	1.09	.057	.867	.752
Google Doc	233	3	1	4	2.04	.039	.591	.349
Dropbox	233	3	1	4	2.73	.046	.708	.502
Google drive	233	3	1	4	3.04	.038	.575	.330
Google Calendar	233	3	1	4	2.86	.045	.683	.467
Bookafy	233	3	1	4	1.78	.049	.744	.553
Buffer	233	3	1	4	1.09	.053	.805	.648
Computer	233	3	1	4	3.06	.043	.650	.423
Laptop	233	3	1	4	2.80	.048	.730	.532
Internet	233	3	1	4	3.09	.048	.738	.544
Phone	233	3	1	4	3.00	.047	.710	.504
E-payment	233	3	1	4	2.97	.053	.804	.646
E-wallet	233	3	1	4	2.46	.055	.835	.698
E-banking	233	3	1	4	2.71	.053	.809	.654
Card Payment	233	3	1	4	2.74	.056	.857	.735
Valid N (listwise)	233							

Field survey, 2024

Table 2 shows the evolving Technology Tools used for administrative service delivery. It shows that Zoom, as a high mean of 3.03, while Google meet and WhatsApp as a mean of 2.84 and 2.77 respectively. Telegram, Meetio, Bookafy and Buffer as a low mean of 1.81, 1.09, 1.78 and 1.09 respectively while Computer, Internet, phones, e-payment, e-wallet, e-banking and card payment have a high mean of 3.06, 2.80, 3.09, 3.00, 2.97, 2.46, 2.71 and 2.74 respectively

Table 2: Administrative Processes in the selected Tertiary Institutions

Descriptive Statistics

	N	Minimu m	Maximu m	Mean	Std. Deviation
Admission Processes	233	1	4	3.27	.645
Computer Based Test	233	1	4	3.06	.689
Examination Management	233	1	4	3.23	.740
School Fees Payment	233	1	4	3.04	.634
Information Dissemination	233	1	4	3.27	.648
Records Management	233	1	4	2.32	.604
Financial Probity	233	1	4	3.31	.731
Valid N (listwise)	233				

Field survey, 2024

The above table shows the administrative processes being carried out by the non-teaching staff in the selected Tertiary Institution. It shows that Admission Processes, Computer Based Test, Examination Management, School Fees payment, Information Dissemination, Financial Probity all has a high mean of 3.27, 3.06, 3.23, 3.04, 3.27 and 3.31 respectively while the mean for Records Management is 2.32.

Table 3: Influence of Evolving Technology on Administrative Service Delivery
Descriptive Statistics

	N	Mini	Max	Mean	Std. Deviation
It enhances quick decision making	233	1	4	3.29	0.720
It enhances quick retrieval of documents	233	1	4	3.20	0.679
It enhances quick dissemination of information	233	1	4	3.30	0.604
It facilitate real-time collaboration	233	1	4	3.24	0.630
Information can be retrieved anytime and anywhere	233	1	4	3.17	0.734
It saves time	233	1	4	3.41	0.610
It promote accuracy	233	1	4	3.41	0.603
It increases efficiency	233	1	4	3.48	0.650
It enhances productivity	233	1	4	3.39	0.621
It facilitates quick access to information	233	1	4	3.08	0.655
It enhance skill development	233	3	4	3.36	0.481
Valid N (listwise)	233				
Source: Field survey 2024					

Table 3 above shows the means score of the influence of evolving Technology on administrative service delivery in the selected Tertiary institution. It enhances quick decision making and quick retrieval of documents as mean of 3.29 and 3.20 respectively. It increases

efficiency as a high mean of 3.48 while it saves time and it promotes accuracy as a mean of 3.41 respectively

Table 4

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	.293 ^a	.186	.182	.750	.186	21.622	1	231	.000

Source: field survey 2024

- a. Predictors: (Constant), Evolving Technology
- b. Dependent Variable: Administrative Service Delivery

ANOVA^b

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	12.177	1	12.177	21.622	.000 ^a
	Residual	130.097	231	.563		
	Total	142.275	232			

- a. Predictors: (Constant), Evolving Technology
- b. Dependent Variable: Administrative Service Delivery

Table 4 presents the results of regression analysis on the influence of Evolving Technology on Administrative Service Delivery of selected Tertiary Institution in Ogun State. The adjusted R Square (R²) suggests that approximately 18.2% of the variance in the administrative service delivery of employees can be explained by the perception of evolving Technology. This shows a weak but positively significant influence of evolving technology on administrative service delivery of Staff. In the same vein, the analysis of variance shows that the regression model is statistically significant ($p < .005$) in explaining the variance in service delivery. It indicates that evolving technology contributes significantly to explaining the variation in service delivery of administrative Staff in selected Tertiary Institutions in Ogun State. This can be seen in the F value (21.622) and the p-value is (.000).

4. DISCUSSION

The evolving Technologies used for administrative service delivery in selected institutions are clearly showed in the results. These include teleconferencing technologies/app like Zoom, Google meet, WhatsApp. Institutions have adopted the use of these teleconferencing tools to pass information, hold meetings and conferences and to carry out other administrative activities. The result also shows that the least used technology/app are bukafy and buffer. These are Calendar and Scheduling Software useful for planning events and activities. Technologies are also used to carry out activities such as e-payment, card payment etc. Tertiary institutions have introduced in different areas the use of Technology in the administration of their institutions. This is why technology has gained prominence globally in the area of information dissemination, teaching, learning, research and public service delivery (Okpowodu, *et. al.*, 2022). This findings was corroborated by Christiana (2018), that evolving technologies are used in organization to foster the dissemination of information and that in this age of booming

technology, running a business without or less technologies is like trying to breathe without lungs therefore it important these institutions make use of these technology to enhance administrative services provided to stakeholders of these institutions.

Administrative services rendered by the selected Tertiary institutions were also confirmed in this study. These include Admission Processes, Computer based Test (CBT), School fees payment, Records, The results show that these institutions are using technology to carry out most administrative services such as purchase of forms, students' registration, payment of fees, result management. The use of technology in admission processes has made the registration exercise less cumbersome and less time-consuming. Computer Based Assessment is now common in these tertiary institutions. According to Bennett (2015), computer-based tests represent a modern way of answering an examination question, replacing the written pen on paper format. Some courses examinations are now Computer Based Test (CBT) to test students' knowledge (Conole & Warburton, 2005). Traditional methods of assessment are being changed by using Technology to assess students of these tertiary institutions (Mubashrah, Tariq & Shami, 2012).

Examination management entails the whole process of administering examinations as well as preservation of results. It comprises of question paper delivery, response storage, marketing of responses, reporting of results from tests or exercises, collation, compilation and computation of results, etc. The study also revealed that these institutions are yet to fully make use of Technology for record keeping as records and mail are still treated manually and this slows down the administrative activities in the institution. Records are not electronically generated, documented or stored for easy retrieval. Most offices still have stalks of files that take up a lot space. Although the study shows that online admission process in the selected tertiary institutions has enhanced enrolment exercises of newly admitted students and make the process less cumbersome; it revealed that online payment of fees though seriously affected by poor infrastructure has enhanced financial probity by blocking leakages and this makes transaction faster and more transparent (Chukwuemeka, Ubochi & Okechukwu, 2017).

On the influence of evolving technology on administrative service delivery in the selected tertiary institutions. The result shows a positive response of quick decision making, quick retrieval of documents, enhances quick dissemination of information, promotes accuracy, enhances productivity enhancement, facilitate real time collaboration. Others include time saving, it productivity enhancement, enhancement of skill development and increase efficiency. This finding supports Akpomi (2019) position that Technology enhances proficiency, productivity and does influence job effectiveness. Technology has improved administrative effectiveness, efficiency and accuracy in service delivery (Jimoh & Kehinde, 2025; Kingsley et al 2022; Akpoiroro & Okpowodu 2017; Zain, 2014). Services such as payment of school fees, online lectures, dissemination and retrieval of information, conferences and meetings can be carried out using evolving technology.

The tested hypothesis indicates that there is a weak but positive significant influence of evolving technology on administrative service delivery of employees in the selected tertiary institutions. The results show the regression analysis on the influence of Evolving Technology on Administrative Service Delivery of selected Tertiary Institution in Ogun State. The positive significance suggests that there is indeed a relationship between evolving technology and administrative service delivery. The adjusted R Square (R²) suggests that approximately 18.2% of the variance in the administrative service delivery of employees can be explained by the perception of evolving Technology. This shows a weak but positively significant influence of

evolving technology on administrative service delivery of Staff. In the same vein, the analysis of variance shows that the regression model is statistically significant ($p < .005$) in explaining the variance in service delivery. It indicates that evolving technology contributes significantly to explaining the variation in service delivery of employees in selected Tertiary Institutions in Ogun State. In this context, evolving technology refers to various factors such as computers, phones, Apps, and internet facilities which impact the overall quality of administrative service to stakeholders. This result implies that as these factors usage increase or improve, administrative services also tend to increase. This can be seen in the F value (21.622) and the p-value is (.000). Therefore, the null hypothesis that states that Evolving Technology does not have influence on administrative service delivery is rejected.

5. CONCLUSION AND POLICY RECCOMENDATIONS

The findings demonstrate that a successful administrative operation is dependent on availability and usage of digital technology, especially in the dissemination of information, meeting coordination, admission process, fee payment systems and examination management. The broad adoption of electronic payment systems and teleconferencing facilities is a pointer to the increasing shift towards digitally dominated administration which is linked to the global pattern in the management of higher education. The study reveals that clear gaps remain in some strategic areas like records management and digital documentation despite the benefits enjoyed from the adoption of technology by several administrative functions such as transparency, accountability, effectiveness and efficiency. Relying on traditional mode of record keeping affects administrative efficiency and effectiveness, retard decision making processes and will impede the opportunity attached to the digital transformation in higher education. The weak but positive significant relationship between the variables shows that the adoption of technology alone is not enough to drive improvement, but must be complemented by factors such as human and material capacity and management policy systems. Primarily, the results suggest that evolving technology positively influences administrative service delivery in institutions, though this influence is constrained by different challenges in infrastructure, organization and implementation. However, to leverage the benefits accrued to digitalization, tertiary institutions must encourage extensive digital inclusion, engage resources in robust infrastructure and enhance institutional abilities for efficient use of technology. The improvement of administrative performance will be achieved through stakeholders' satisfaction and sustainable administration.

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